

21st-CENTURY MATHEMATICS AND MATHEMATICS EDUCATION: DECIPHERING THE CONFUSION

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Abstract

The article aims to create a concise document that illustrates the debate between mathematics and mathematics education and clears the muddle by synthesizing the literature on the subject. A desk review guided by an iterative literature search procedure and thematic analysis was conducted. "Mathematics and mathematics education" was the initial search key term. Numerous mathematicians and mathematics educators are paying attention to the discussion. The development of mathematics education as a subject of study or a teaching profession has been aided by numerous academic disciplines, including mathematics, philosophy, psychology, sociology, and anthropology. Both communities are interested in advancing mathematics's cultural transformation for the greater good of society, which reflects their shared concerns and areas of common interest. Conversely, there have been a great deal of discussions between various groups within the two communities; some of these discussions have been beneficial, but some have been harmful. Thus, a subsequent discussion focuses on evidence and reasoning, respectful exchange of ideas, willingness to modify views based on new arguments, and one aimed at clarity and improvement rather than victory will have added value to best benefit from the development. The pull-apart observed in Ethiopia is not unique or out of the ordinary. The study suggested a three-circle structure for collaborative work that covers several topics, including mathematical modeling, discoveries in mathematics, and the history of mathematics.

Keywords: Mathematics, Mathematics Education, Professional Development, Three Circle Framework.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mathematics as a subject of study is taught as a compulsory subject in primary, secondary schools and university in Ethiopia. Mathematics is also one of the subjects that are compulsory at national examinations. Although a pass in mathematics is not a requirement for candidates to enter higher education, passing mathematics offers increased opportunities to candidates. Similarly, entry into most of the university programmes requires learners to have obtained a good grade in mathematics. The big questions here may rise is what the difference between mathematics and mathematics education? is the philosophy makes them difference or the same? This paper sought to elite something the confusion that rose for a number of decades by educators.

The debate between mathematics and mathematics education is as old as the history of mathematics education. This worldwide issue has taken the attention of many mathematicians and mathematics educators. The issue is not only educational and

professional but also influenced by political decisions. With the political change in Ethiopia for instance, the education policy was also changed and attention had been given to the educational approach including more emphasis on pedagogical courses on teacher training from 2004 to 2010. Later on, a political decision was made that reversed such emphasis to pedagogical courses for teachers' preparation, especially for secondary school teachers, which includes the change of the degree nomenclature (Bachelor of Education (BEd) to Bachelor of Science (BSc) and Master of Education (MEd) to Master of Science (MSc)).

The reverse changed the course combination from major subjects and pedagogical courses to purely major subjects in the respective field of study. As a result, while the mathematics and science education departments had vanished, the quality of education declined (Yenealem, 2018). In 2018 a new education roadmap was prepared (Teferra et al., 2018). The roadmap gave attention to teachers' education that re-reverses the curriculum document. Following the motivation of the roadmap and some other emphasis on mathematics and science education and teachers' education, the mathematics department at our university has taken the initiative to launch a postgraduate program (PGP) in mathematics education.

As part of the preparation, we conducted a need assessment survey that facilitates the decision on the program and program document preparation. As part of that initiative, we have raised many questions including the challenges that we have been facing from the mathematicians, where to place the PGP in mathematics education, pillars of the program document, and the like. To have a comprehensive picture of these questions we tend to see the international trend about the debate between mathematics and mathematics education as a result to clear the muddle in the Ethiopian context. With this background, the paper tries to attain the following objectives:

2. GENERAL OBJECTIVES

To investigate the exist debate between Mathematics and Mathematics Education and clearing the Muddle.

2.1 Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of this study were:

- a. To identify the causes of the distinction between debates regarding mathematics and mathematics education.
- b. To examine common ground between mathematics and mathematics education.
- c. To synthesize lessons to be learned about the relationship between mathematics and mathematics education if any.

3. METHOD AND MATERIAL

The purpose of this study is to investigate and outline existing materials, including different study types on the debate between mathematics and mathematics education.

With due attention to the quality aspect of the literature identified, the study seeks to uncover debates, trends, and key concepts in a thematic synthesis approach to summarize the findings for implications in practice, future research, and policy analysis.

3.1 Searching Strategy

This paper is mainly a desk-based review, considering both academic and grey literature. While global documents retrieved from international source country-specific policy documents, official information's and communications were also incorporated and some part of the study was published (see Sebsibe et al, 2023).

Materials that contain details about the debate between mathematics and mathematics education program were taken into account. Individual documents selection was guided by an iterative process as proposed by Miles and Huberman (2014). A multiple literature search was conducted, using electronics database searches. Keyword searches were done on Google, Google Scholar, Education Resources Information Centre (ERIC), Scopus databases and research gate. Initial searching term "mathematics and mathematics education" was used. The documents obtained from these sources were used as primary sources. The searching was extended by referring to reference lists of pre-reviewed documents; and contacting the authors of some studies (via research gate and academia web pages).

3.2 Document Retrieval

The terms "mathematics and mathematics education " were used to search for specific documents in the specified databases. The search encompasses articles, conference presentations, book chapters, thesis, reports, handbooks, and country-specific official reports written in English without time limit. Subsequently, the search was expanded by reviewing the reference lists of the identified articles. This process was further supported by using searches on ResearchGate and other official websites, as well as alternative search terms.

The search was conducted entirely in an iterative manner (one after another), which made it unsystematic. Studies that are freely available or have open access for full document retrieval were included. On the other hand, documents where full document retrieval was unavailable were excluded. Nevertheless, after removal of duplications and documents with no relevant quotations the final review of the accumulated 32 materials consisting of twelve journal articles, seven books, two book chapter, five reports (Notices), two conference proceedings, and two handbook, and two policy documents. In addition, policy documents and government reports were consulted to substantiate the arguments.

3.3 Data Analysis

The smaterials chosen for the final analysis were reviewed multiple times, with highlighting key points in the PDF documents using different colours. Following that, a data extraction table was created, featuring a header row with the following categories: Authors name, year of publication, document type (empirical, review, book, book chapter,

report, conference paper, handbook, and policy document), title, main objective, quotations about the debate between mathematics and mathematics education.

A thematic review, which is a type of systematic review, is a powerful tool to make informed decisions about claims based on a qualitative explanation of the existing information about a problem (Thomas & Harden, 2008). The explanatory nature does not depend on the number of studies included, but rather on the depth and breadth of the studies selected for the review. Thus, a thematic review was employed as the primary method for analysing the textual data, enabling a more profound examination of meaning beyond the words, thereby assisting in achieving the study's objectives.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Mathematicology: Mathematics as an Object of Research

According to Uchegbu (2014) mathematicology is the philosophical and critical study of mathematics's nature, growth, and cultural significance, particularly concerning indigenous knowledge systems and ways of knowing. Thus, in the debate of mathematics and mathematics education, the mathematicology should never be permitted to lose sight of the other pole of the relationship which mathematics education is about: the human being. The idea that an incomplete or even incorrect explanation may yield more insight for the mathematics educator than a rigorous proof runs counter to the way of thinking in a discipline that gives little credit to a justification which is not a proof. On the other hand, mathematicians do give weight to proof, even a heuristic argument, which actually persuades them of the truth of mathematical claims. Proofs must have in some sense pedagogical value. From the mathematicology point of view, we clearly see that the two poles (Mathematics and Mathematics Education) are collaborating between each other.

4.2 Emergence of Mathematics Education as a Field of Study

The origin of mathematics dates back to the origins of humankind and its development just intertwined with the development of human civilization (Karp & Schubring, 2014). While the question 'what is mathematics' is the basis of the philosophy of mathematics, Reuben Hersh in a book entitled what is mathematics, really? From a humanist point of view described it as 'a social-cultural-historical entity' (Hersh, 1997 p.249). Hersh went on saying '*Study of the lawful, predictable, parts of the social-conceptual world also have a name: mathematics* (p. 18)'. Nowadays, it is a school subject taught by nearly all students in the world (Furinghetti et al., 2012).

Different reforms took place in the lifetime of mathematics but the 19th-century educational reforms basically influenced the mathematics community and the perspectives of the general community on mathematics, which finally led to the development of mathematics education as a field of research and field of study (Furinghetti, et al., 2012). The 20th century reforms which are of course the continuation of the 19th-century reforms were the foundation of the emergence of mathematics education either as a field of teaching profession, a field of research, a field of professional development (teachers education), or a scientific field of study. The field (as a research field or field of study) developed and

evolved in challenging times (the time of the Industrial Revolution, 1760 -1840) and contributed a lot in terms of theoretical development and practical applications. Nowadays, the field has its own theory, framework, and principles (Lowrie, 2015; Yenealem, 2019). Although many disciplines (mathematics, philosophy, psychology, sociology, anthropology) contributed a lot to the development of mathematics education as an independent field of study, it faced challenges and resistance both from the mathematics community and from the broader education disciplines as it proceeded in subsequent years (Furinghetti, et al., 2012).

4.3 The Main Driving Forces of the 20th Century Reforms and its Achievements

While the demand for mathematical literacy increased following the industrialization of the job market, the number of students interested in joining fields of study that demand mathematics declined. For instance, in the United States of America (USA), numeracy problems in lower grades, decline of secondary school students to take mathematics courses, the so-called "math avoidance", 50% failure among college calculus students had been recorded (Schoenfeld, 2004). In particular, the rising demand to divide teaching and research, and the need to professionalize researchers in mathematics (Furinghetti, et al., 2012), changes in cultural and social settings and hence changes in 'forms of thinking' i.e. paradigm shift of epistemology after the French Revolution (from 1789 to 1799 or end of the 18th century) (Schoenfeld, 2004), the shift in the responsibility of knowledge transformation i.e., Individual, family, or religious to a public issue under the responsibility of government (Green, 2013) were among the driving forces to educational reforms in 20th century.

Besides, the rising demand and interest to solve innate problems in the education system in a way that addresses the rising modernization of nations, which in turn created professional unions, specific journals, and associations, were also contributed to the reforms. Moreover, the rising interest to change ways of communication among mathematicians (from individual and private to academics and societies in the form of proceedings and reports), the establishment of ICMI (International Commission on Mathematics Instruction) in 1908 and themes of priorities for intervention as listed in the ICMI between 1908 and 1915 were deriving forces that contributed to the reform which in turn added value to strengthening the mathematics education community. Above all the need to correct the misconceptions about the nature of mathematics in the larger population as observed by educators (Furinghetti et al, 2012; Hersh, 1997) was also the driving force of the reforms.

The debates and the reforms throughout the 19th century transferred to the 20th century and in the first half of the 20th century there also basic debates and actions including The John Perry movement in England and outside of England (basically, in Japan and the USA), the standardization of content and methods of the school curriculum in the USA, the movement to humanize mathematics including integrating it with life science and the dropdown of differential and integral calculus to secondary school syllabus in France.

At the beginning of the second half of the 20th century parallel modern mathematics movements were conducted in different parts of the world. The launching of Sputnik in 1957 intensified concern for further and serious reforms in different nations (Schoenfeld, 2004). Attention was shifted to active learning, the use of concrete teaching aids, the democratization of mathematics, and active participation of teachers, in particular, in the USA, a new school curriculum and in the Nordics a new syllabus had been designed, ICME recognized mathematics education as a legitimate field of science nexus between mathematical and pedagogical contents, the journal of Educational Studies in Mathematics was found in 1968, which is now reached 118 volumes in March 2025 and have more than 10 million documents (<https://www.springer.com/journal/10649>). Its establishment motivated others and The International Journal on Mathematics Education was first published in 1969, and the Journal for Research in Mathematics Education (JRME) was first published in 1970. Moreover, as in Furinghetti et al., (2012, p. 286) mathematics and hence mathematics instruction ‘... was perceived by governments as linked to an important potential for powering among nations’.

The activities performed in the first half of the century were focused on curriculum reforms. In the 1950s not only the teaching and learning, but also the research in mathematics education had got attention and made changes in attention and direction. Moreover, the market demand for human power with basic knowledge and skill in mathematics increased, which brought more societal demand for mathematics, and achievement in mathematics was considered as a tool to secure power among nations (Furinghetti, et al, 2012). As compared to the growing demand for mathematics at an individual or collective level, the efforts made so far were evaluated as insufficient and a new initiative was called which opened the room to develop mathematics education both as a legitimate research field and a field of study (Furinghetti, et al, 2012).

4.4 The Main Reforms

As a result of those demands, many changes were made. In particular, many associations, journals, publishers, and publications, modern communications channels were formed, and contributed to at least tackling problems at a national level. The new restructuring demanded attention on curriculum reforms based on the growing relationship between parts of programs, relationships between mathematics and the other disciplines including new findings about children’s development and focus on applications of curriculum contents to real-life situations (Furinghetti, et al, 2012). Ways forwarded by the mathematics education research community have gotten recognition. For instance, John Perry’s idea of ‘practical mathematics’, in England was adopted in Japan and USA. As part of the reform in France and then in Germany calculus concepts were pulled down from university to secondary school curriculum. In the USA, (entitled New Mathematics Movement) a new school curriculum (the 1950s–1970s) was designed, France, the United Kingdom (entitled School Mathematics Project), and West Germany have also made amendments to their existing curriculum and school practice. In doing so, the recognition of international cooperation, experience sharing and benchmarking, and curriculum comparison also got attention.

In all those reforms while mathematics educators had got attention and played a great role, mathematicians who supported research in mathematics education and those who gave attention to pedagogic aspects in the teaching-learning of mathematics also contributed a lot (Goldin, 2003).

At this time the mathematics education community already has got recognition from the policy makers and policy making. The foundation and all subsequent progress of mathematics education were made by great mathematicians (Felix Klein, Jacques Hadamard, George Pólya, Hans Freudenthal, Nicolas Rouche, André Revuz, Georges Glaeser and mathematics teachers (Bass, 2005; Fried, 2014; Hodgson et al., 2016). In the early stage of the development, all policy, curriculum, and pedagogical issues were determined by mathematicians and mathematics educators.

4.5 What Causes the Distinction?

Besides the political, social, and economic demands of the reform, the new curriculum brought a new outlook and approach to mathematics and mathematics teaching, including shifts in **epistemological**, **methodological**, and **focus of attention** that affected and divided the mathematics community. In particular, this shift was not well accepted by the mathematicians and caused resistance and opposition, which later led to two distinct communities of professionals. The distinction falls in one of the two categories:

- Mathematics/mathematicians which include university mathematics teachers, research mathematicians, and scientists in mathematics,
- Mathematics education (also named as didactics of mathematics, mathematics teaching, or pedagogy of mathematics with a little difference in context) includes mathematics education researchers, curriculum development experts, teacher educators, and K-12 mathematics teachers (Fried, 2014; Goldin, 2003).

4.6 Outlooks of one to Another

Mathematics education has been developed as an approach to overcoming difficulties that mathematics teaching was facing. But since its inception, although great mathematicians contributed to its development, it is not welcomed by others. As time went on, the mathematics educators themselves intentionally or unintentionally contributed to the distinction and to the pull apart of the two communities. The question, “are the two fields really distinct?” itself was and still is an issue of debate. With this regard, Bass and Hodgson (2004, p. 640) said the two are distinct but linked, saying that *‘Mathematics education and mathematics, though obviously linked, are fundamentally different as domains of practice and scholarship’*. Ted Eisenberg as in Fried (2014, p. 4) emphasizes the similarity by saying: *‘the divide between the two communities is wasteful and unhealthy for both’*. So, how do the mathematicians consider themselves, the mathematics and the mathematics education and vice-versa?

Mathematicians overconfident in their content knowledge for teaching and may ignoring pedagogical knowledge. While some accept the limitation of content knowledge for teaching and recognize pedagogical knowledge and educational research, many remain

doubtful or dismissive of mathematics education researchers. This scepticism may be due to doubts about methodologies or a refusal to accept evidence-based findings, even when they are scientifically valid (Ball et al., 2008; Schoenfeld, 2004). Additionally, while some mathematicians accept the limitation of content knowledge for teaching and recognize mathematics education research and researchers, others ignore equity between content knowledge and pedagogical knowledge and continue in their practice i.e., keep mathematics teaching as it had been (Ernest, 2018; Gutstein, 2006; Ladson-Billings, 1997).

On the other hand, mathematics educators face several challenges in establishing the legitimacy and identity of their field. Accordingly, one significant issue was lack of confidence in accepting the field as a full-fledged field of specialization. In this regard, Fried (2014, p.5) mentioned that *'While the separation may be merely bureaucratic and not essential, members of the new field do need to consider their own identity as mathematics educators.* Another concern is the lack providing evidence-based justification to resolve controversies in policy and practice, which often undermines the impact and credibility of their contributions. Moreover, mathematics educators leave little room for mathematics itself, and mathematicians, moved too far from mathematics content to sociocultural political and economic scenarios (Fried, 2014). Moreover, the fragmentation of research issues in the field of mathematics education results in a lack of coherent direction, which complicates the establishment of a unified theoretical basis (Schoenfeld, 2000).

There is also an increasing gap between researchers and practitioners, with research findings from mathematics education research are not effectively incorporated into classroom practice (Kilpatrick, 1992). This difference might cause frustration among teachers who feel supported by research yet alienated from scholarly dialogues. Furthermore, external factors like high-stakes assessments and standardized curricula often restrict the scope of mathematics education, limiting opportunities for innovative and context-sensitive teaching approaches (Boaler, 2002).

Besides, both communities have different perspectives in terms of knowledge view, content/idea of curriculum, teaching approach, research focus, research methodology, the aim of teaching, and ways forwarded to overcome difficulties in mathematics teaching and learning. For many mathematicians, mathematics is singular (Platonic paradigm), mathematics is certain, cumulative, and untouched by social interests. For them, mathematics is a lens through which one can look at the world, more generally, mathematics is merely a body of knowledge or an academic discipline with a narrow view (either pure or applied). On the other hand, for mathematics educators, mathematics is plural (humanistic paradigm) and hence has a social aspect, with cultural limitations to its claims of certainty, universality and absoluteness.

More generally, one looks at mathematics through the lens of learners (and teachers). It is a body of knowledge or an academic discipline and also a field of practice, an all-inclusive view (concerned with what is it, how it is learned, understood, used, or integrated with real life) (Ernest, 2018). The different views of mathematics and mathematics

education are summarised in Table 1 (Bass & Hodgson, 2004; Eisenberg & Fried, 2009; Ernest, 2018; Fried, 2014; Selden, 2002; Wittmann, 2021).

Table 1: Different views of mathematics and mathematics education

No	Viewpoint	Mathematician	Mathematics educators
1	Nature of Mathematics & Mathematical Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Platonic paradigm (mathematics is singular) ▪ Mathematics is certain, cumulative, and untouched by social interests ▪ Mathematics is a lens through which one can look at the world ▪ Mathematics is merely a body of knowledge or an academic discipline ▪ Narrow view (either pure, or applied, but on his/her specialization) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Humanistic paradigm (mathematics is plural) ✓ Mathematics is social, with cultural limitations to its claims of certainty, universality, and absoluteness ✓ One looks at mathematics through the lens of learners (and teachers). ✓ Mathematics is a body of knowledge, or an academic discipline, and also a field of practice ✓ All-inclusive view (concerned with what it is, how it is learned, understood, used or integrated with real life)
2	Curriculum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content and ideas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content, culture, and experience
3	Teaching approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding is context-independent • Students make new conjectures, prove new theorems, and find new insights • Teacher-centred • Discourage ethno-mathematical practices • Focus on gifted & fittest students • Do not consider theories of learning and thinking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Teaching/learning/understanding is context-laden, i.e., understanding has individual and social aspects/is integrated with culture and everyday context ▪ Student-centred ▪ Encourage ethno-mathematical practices ▪ Inclusive approach ▪ Consider theories of learning and thinking to enhance understanding and attitude
4	Professional development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content knowledge and pedagogy integration
5	Research domain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prove theorems or establish the truth of theorems (pure) ▪ Problem solving/design applications to science and technology (applied) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ How students learn and develop understandings ✓ Contribute to establishing educational policies and standards.
6	Research methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rarely consider different philosophical/theoretical perspectives/there is a 'gold standard' (Selden, 2002 P.11) • The scientific research paradigm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Usually considers different philosophical/theoretical perspectives/ ▪ The interpretative research paradigm

The way mathematicians and mathematics educators' view tackling the challenges students face are different. Mathematicians design mathematical science fields of study that integrate mathematics (pure and applied) with other subjects like statistics, financial mathematics, and teachers' education. Mathematics educators, on the other hand, work to change the attitude of students from the very beginning.

One drawback of the distinction is the placement of mathematics education in universities that lack consistency (Ernest, 2018). In most parts of the world, mathematics education has been placed in the faculty of education, with the social sciences or even the humanities (for instance, in both Australia and New Zealand (Lowrie, 2015), and in other parts in the faculty of natural science blended with mathematics.

With regard to the placement issue, someone may say as far as they are part of a university, what makes the difference? However, the issue is big as the faculties' worldviews and methodological approaches are quite different. The social sciences and humanities and the exact sciences have their own sense of knowledge, what it means to know something and what one needs to do to know something are quite different. With this regard, ICME (International Congress on Mathematical Education) mentioned that '*. . . mathematics education to be given a place in suitable mathematical departments of universities or research institutes*' (Furinghetti, et al, 2012, p. 287).

Whatever is said so far about the distinction, the point is that they have common interests and shared concerns: both are interested in enhancing the cultural transformation of mathematics for the best benefit of the larger society.

Thus, the question to be raised is can't they find a common ground so that they work in collaboration for the common benefit and fast-track their achievement? Until now, there have been so many debates among different segments of the two communities to clear the muddle, while some of the debates were constructive others were destructive (Ball et al, 2005). For instance,

- Several symposiums were conducted (For instance, in 2012 at Ben Gurion University of the Negev),
- The longitudinal study conducted by Elena Nardi (Nardi, 2008),
- A range of cross-sectional studies was conducted (Sfard, 1998, Artigue & Winsløw, 2010; Goldin, 2003; Ball et al, 2005),
- Obstacles to collaborations have been identified (separate placement of the two communities in different departments basically at universities and research institutes, teaching different courses, not meeting professionally i.e.publishing in different journals, attending different conferences),
- Common grounds have been identified (proof, history of mathematics, educational policy, curriculum, affect, equity),
- Common projects were conducted (Dörfler, 2003; Viirman, 2018),

- Suggestions have been provided:
 - Mathematics education needs to stay close to mathematics, needs to engage more systematically with disseminating its outputs, avoid complicating recommendations, and make it free from jargon.
 - Mathematics needs to recognize the benefit of research in students' teaching and learning, accept the socioeconomic aspects of teaching and learning, inclusiveness, and modern development in learning theory.
 - Both should be open-minded to clear the muddle, conduct joint projects, and work on the identified common grounds.

4.7 The Lessons we have to Learn

The pull-apart that has seen in Ethiopia is not special and abnormal. A lot is expected from both communities to clear the muddle with those who have a positive outlook or optimism about the distinction and accept the common interest and shared concern among the two campuses. The philosophical paradigm of mathematics education is more appropriate to the social sciences and humanities than the natural sciences. However, mathematics education has to share more from the mathematics department in terms of human and material resources than the departments in social science and humanities. Thus, mathematics education should be placed in the College of Natural and Computational Sciences. We have to make clear ourselves, our staff members, and our perspective students on:

- What is it a mathematics educator has to do well?
- What makes a mathematics educator an expert?
- What are the distinctions between mathematics and mathematics education (what do mathematicians need to know about mathematics educators and vice-versa)?
- What are the common grounds of the two communities?
- What are the possible areas of collaboration for two communities to work together in terms of research, teaching, professional development, and community service and engagement?

At Ethiopian Universities, mathematics teachers' training has been given more attention to pure mathematics rather than mathematics education until 2021. Currently, the Ministry of Education (MoE) have shown the commitment doing well in the education sector and hence not only on mathematics education but also on the other science subjects likes chemistry education, physics education and biology education. This is manifested through the assignment of one university (Kotebe Education University (KEU)) as an Education University that is intended to serve as a centre of excellence for education and teachers training (Sebsibe et al, 2023). Besides, the MoE has developed a curriculum framework for teachers' education. The document mentioned importance of incorporating both subject area and professional courses to produce a competent teacher (MoE, 2022).

Following the reforms, all departments at KEU, which were previously a metropolitan university, developed a curriculum which is appropriate for teachers training. The mathematics department of KEU, in its rational of on a Masters of Education program document, mentioned that the country needs to produce qualified professionals who can teach and conduct research in mathematics and mathematics education. This is an opportunity for mathematics education experts in the country to reveal the blessing and to promote the field. Thus, a subsequent discussion focuses on evidence and reasoning, respectful exchange of ideas, willingness to modify views based on new arguments, and one aimed at clarity and improvement rather than victory will have added value to best benefit from the development.

5. CONCLUSION

Although resistance and partiality disintegrate the two fields, they are highly related and can't be disassociated and no one was and will not be profitable from the pull apart. Collaboration brings a win-win situation for members of both communities in particular and the larger society in general. Mathematicians have to recognize the role of mathematics education researchers and mathematics educators have to leave politics for politicians and have to focus on the built-in concepts of the discipline.

After all the efforts made so far to clear the muddle, even though there are some improvements and promising start-ups (common to see joint research projects, department having both professionals, recognition of each by the other as a legitimate field of study, using the output of one as an input for the other), there is much left to go and pave the way. Furthermore, the field still needs the collaboration of the two communities because of one or more of the following reasons:

- The number of students who need to join mathematics has been declining.
- The number of graduates who join mathematics teaching and the turnover has been decreasing.
- Equity in mathematics is still a sensitive and unaddressed issue.
- The demand for meaningful and accelerated enhancement in mathematics in particular and STEM education, in general, is high.

Common grounds and themes for collaboration work include but are not limited to the history of mathematics, mathematical literacy, problem solving, imagination visualization and creativity, justification and proof, technology integration, the mathematics curriculum, the education policy in the lens of mathematics, professional development, new insights in mathematics and mathematical modelling.

Figure1 shows the relationship between mathematics education and mathematics possible areas of collaboration: research (technology, problem solving, imagination visualization, and creativity, assessments), curriculum and instructional materials, teaching approaches, professional development (teachers training, CPD), and community service and engagement (preserving mathematical indigenous knowledge).

Lastly, the study proposed three circle framework that indicates the relationship between Mathematics education and mathematics even though the experts between the two are in different circles.

Figure 1: Proposed three circle framework: Relationship between mathematics education and mathematics.

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